

Reactions of Carbon-Nucleophiles with Acetylenic Esters and Ketones

A. S. A. YOUSSEF, K. A. KANDEEL and HASSAN M. F. MADKOUR*

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Abbassia, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 27 April 1992, revised 29 September 1993, accepted 9 November 1993

Cyanoacetanilide (1) reacted with 3-phenyl-1-aryl-prop-2-yn-1-ones (2a-c) in the presence of sodium pellets in dry benzene to give the corresponding 3-cyanopyrid-2-ones (3a-c) and the aminopyrid-2-ones (4a,b). Similarly 1 reacted with methyl 3-arylprop-2-ynoates (2d,e) to give the 5-cyanopyrid-2-ones (7a,b) and the pyran-2-ones (8). On the other hand, 6-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylcoumarin (9) reacted with 2a-c,e to give the corresponding 3-amino-4-aryl or carbomethoxy-8-chloro-5-arylbenzo[c]coumarin (10a-d) as well as the propenylcoumarins (11) and the benzo[c]coumarins (12). In all cases the reactions seem to take place via Michael addition.

In continuation of the studies on the reaction of active methylene compounds with acetylenic esters and ketones¹, the present work reports the reaction of cyanoacetanilide (1) and 6-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylcoumarin² (9) with 3-phenyl-1-arylprop-2-yn-1-ones (2a-c) and methyl 3-arylprop-2-ynoates (2d,e).

Reaction of 1 with 2a-e : 3-Phenyl-1-arylprop-2-yn-1-ones (2a-c) were refluxed with cyanoacetanilide (1) in the presence of sodium pellets in dry benzene to give the corresponding 6-

aryl-3-cyano-1,4-diphenylpyrid-2-ones (3a-c) and 4-amino-5-aryl-6-phenylpyrid-2-ones (4a,b). The structures of the compounds were established by spectroscopic and analytical data (Table 1). However, the treatment of 2b with 1 in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine at room temperature gave 3-phenylformamido-6-(*p*-anisyl)-4-phenyl-2H-pyran-2-one (5 and 6) (Table 1). The formation of the pyran-2-one (5) can be explained through a Michael addition of the carbanion of 1 to 2b and hydrolysis of the cyano group to carboxylic group followed by cyclisation. The con-

figuration of **6** was proved to be *E* on the basis of the deshielding of the methine proton which appears at δ 6.4³ (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL, INFRARED (cm⁻¹) AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA*

Compd no	M p ** °C	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{NII/OH}$	δ
3a	189–91 ^a	1 670	2 230		3 60 (3H, s, OMe)
3b	198–200 ^b	1 670	2 230		6 35 (1H, s, =CH) 6 55–7 80 (14H, m, ArH)
3c	212–14 ^b	1 665	2 230		
4a	217–19 ^a	1 690, 1 670		3 220, 3 290	
4b	180–82 ^c	1 690, 1 670		3 220, 3 350	
5	223–25 ^b	1 725, 1 680		3 300	3 90 (3H, s, OMe) 6 80 (1H, s, =CH) 6 90–8 00 (15H, m, ArH, NH)
6	125–27 ^d	1 665			2 15 (6H, m, -(CH ₂) ₃ -) 3 71 (4H, m, CH ₂ -N-CH ₂) 4 22 (3H, s, OMe) 6 40 (1H, s, =CH) 7 15–8.4 (9H, m, ArH)
7a	268–70 ^b	1 670	2 230	3 620	
7b	278–80 ^d	1 670	2 230	3 620	5 70 (1H, s, =CH) 6 85–7 70 (9H, m, ArH) 11 70 (1H, br, OH)
8	228–30 ^c	1 720	2 230	3 300	
10a	212–14 ^c	1 730, 1 695		3 330, 3 450	
10b	186–88 ^c	1 740, 1 690		3 330, 3 450	3 75 (3H, s, OMe) 6 50–8 00 (15H, m, ArH, NH ₂)
10c	226–28 ^f	1 735, 1 695		3 330, 3 440	
10d	195–97 ^b	1 730, 1 720		3 350, 3 470	
11	226–28 ^c	1 735, 1 700	2 230		2 20 (2H, s, CH ₂) 6 71 (1H, s, =CH) 7 00–8 00 (12H, m, ArH)
12	255–57 ^f	1 730, 1 690		3 280	
13	107–09 ^d	1 730, 1 705, 1 640			1 75 (6H, m, -(CH ₂) ₃ -) 2 45 (3H, s, CH ₃) 3 20 (4H, t, CH ₂ -N-CH ₂) 7 1–7 7 (3H, m, ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

**Solvent for crystallisation - ^abenzene, ^bethanol, ^cmethanol, ^dpetrol (b p 60–80°), ^e(methanol + benzene), ^f(benzene + petrol).

On the other hand, methyl 3-arylprop-2-ynoates (**2d,e**) were found to react with cyanoacetanilide **1** in the presence of sodium pellets in dry benzene to give the corresponding 4-aryl-5-cyano-6-hydroxy-

1-phenylpyrid-2-ones (**7a,b**) and 6-anilino-4-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-5-cyano-2*H*-pyran-2-one (**8**). Chemical and spectroscopic evidence support the structure of the pyrid-2-one derivatives (**7a,b**) (Table 1). The existence of **7** in an enol-keto tautomerism was established by spectral data (Table 1), and chemically as their solutions gave a colour with FeCl₃ solution. The structure of **8** was established from its infrared and analytical data (Table 1). The existence of the tautomerism form (enolic one) of **8** was proved chemically as its alcoholic solution gave a violet colour with FeCl₃ solution.

Reaction of 9 with 2a-c,e : Treatment of 6-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylcoumarin (**9**) with **2a-c,e** in the presence of sodium ethoxide in dry ether at room temperature gave 3-amino-4-aryloxy (or carbomethoxy)-8-chloro-5-arylbenzo[*c*]coumarin (**10a-d**) and 3-cyano-6-chloro-4-(3'-*p*-chlorobenzoyl-2'-phenyl-1'-propenyl)coumarin (**11**) in addition to 4-(*p*-chlorobenzoyl)-8-chloro-3-imino-5-phenyl-4-hydro-3*H*-benzo[*c*]coumarin (**12**).

The structures of **10a-d** were substantiated from analytical, ir and nmr spectral data (Table 1). The existence of the amino protons in the aromatic region was proved by shaking with D₂O where the number of protons becomes less by two. The deshielding effect for the two amino protons can be explained on the basis of the hydrogen bonding between the two neighbouring carbonyl groups. The structures of the by-products **11** and **12** obtained from the reaction of **9** with **2c** were established from their analytical and spectral data (Table 1). The structure of **12** was rigidly confirmed chemically by its conversion to **10c** in presence of sodium ethoxide in ethanol (cf. Experimental).

On the other hand, the treatment of **9** with **2c** in presence of catalytic amount of piperidine in ethanol, gave 6-chloro-4-methyl-3-piperidylcarbonylcoumarin (**13**) as the only product. The structure of **13** was confirmed by analytical and spectral data (Table 1). The formation of **13** can be explained on the basis of a direct addition of piperidine to the cyano group of **9** followed by hydrolysis.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3 ; except **7b** in DMSO-d_6) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

General procedure for the reaction of 3-phenyl-1-arylprop-2-yn-1-ones (2a-c) and methyl 3-arylprop-2-ynoates (2d,e) with 1 in presence of sodium pellets in dry benzene : Cyanoacetanilide (**1**; 0.005 mol) in dry benzene was refluxed with sodium pellets (0.005 mol) for 2 h, followed by addition of **2a-d** (0.005 mol) and the reflux was continued for ~4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in cold dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The benzene and ether extracts were dried (MgSO_4) and evaporated to give a dark-red viscous oil which solidified when triturated with ethanol. Crystallisation from a proper solvent gave the cyanopyrid-2-one derivatives (**3a-c** and **7a,b**) followed by the aminopyrid-2-one derivatives (**4a,b**) and the pyran-2-one derivative (**8**; Table 1).

Reaction of 3-phenyl-1-anisylprop-2-yn-1-one (2b) with 1 in presence of piperidine in ethanol : A catalytic amount of piperidine (4 drops) was added to a mixture of **1** and **2b** (0.005 mol for both) in ethanol and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature until crystallisation occurred (3 days). The precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol to give **5**. The mother liquor was concentrated to give **6** which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (Table 1).

General procedure for the reaction of 2a-c,e with 9 :

6-Chloro-3-cyano-4-methylcoumarin (**9**; 0.005 mol) was added to powdered sodium ethoxide (0.005 mol) in dry ether whereby an orange colour appeared. The reaction mixture became pink in colour when (**2a-c,e**) (0.005 mol) were added. The mixture was left at room temperature for

72 h and then worked up as mentioned in the previous reaction in presence of sodium pellets in dry benzene. Crystallisation from a proper solvent gave the main products (**10a-d**) (Table 1). In case of the reaction of **2c** with **9**, compound **11** was crystallised first, followed by **10c** and **12**.

Conversion of 12 to 10c : A mixture of **12** (20 mg) and sodium ethoxide in ethanol (7 ml) was kept at room temperature for 4 days. The presence of **10c** was identified by tlc. The reaction mixture was poured in cold dilute HCl, and the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene-petrol to give **10c** which was identified by m.p. and m.m.p. with **10c** (no depression).

Reaction of 3-phenyl-1-(p-chlorophenyl)-prop-2-yn-1-one (2c) with 9 in presence of piperidine in ethanol : To a mixture of **2c** (0.005 mol) and **9** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), a catalytic amount of piperidine (4 drops) was added and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 days. The precipitated solid was filtered and recrystallised from benzene to give **13** as the only product. The mother liquor was concentrated to give unreacted **2c**.

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